

Parvati- the Dance Devotee

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Abstract

The medieval Sanskrit treaties of India have classified dance into three distinct categories, viz., *natya*, *nritya*, and *andhritta*. These texts significantly characterize dancing as masculine or *Tandava* and feminine i.e., *Lasya*. The *Tandava* dance is generally performed for the adoration of the gods. *Lasya*, according to mythology, is the dance movement of goddess Parvati as it manifests joy and ecstasy. This dance signifies beauty, grace, happiness and compassion. The rhythmical steps of this dance are full of harmony, tenderness and are supplementing to the rude male energy of the dance of Shiva. The dance of Parvati has been delineated in sculptural art. This paper intends to highlight a unique metal image of Parvati in her dancing posture.

Key words: Parvati, Shakti, Goddess, Transformation, Nritya, Lasya, Tandav

In the Brahmanical religion, gods and goddesses are paired in such a way that the god is able to fulfill his Dharma (divine purpose) owing to and by the grace of his consort Shakti (feminine power). Brahma is able to create because his wife is the goddess of wisdom, Vishnu sustains and preserves because his wife is the goddess of wealth and abundance. Shiva transcends physical reality and is enlightened because he has got married to Shakti who is incarnated as pure, raw, spiritual energy. In terms of her relationship with Shiva, Shakti personates five different forms: Kali, Durga, Uma, Sati/ Parvati, and the fifth being simply Shakti as all in one.

Parvati, is one of the significant representations of Shakti. The goddess Kali and goddess Durga are incredible, astounding, and terrific forms of Shakti. These goddesses have gained unprecedented importance and popularity in Brahmanical pantheon. They will not be ignored, diminished, or disrespected. Their strength and power are unparalleled. Goddess Parvati is the constant, understated and overwhelming current which cannot be seen on the surface. Like her name, she is the mountain- unmovable; still she is just, regardless of all that exists around her. She is known as a goddess of love, romance, and devotion. Parvati symbolizes devotion, and bhakti. In the Puranic stories her devotion is often touted as solely for her husband. Her husband is the personification of freedom, enlightenment and transcendence. Shakti as Parvati is the love and devotion that gives freedom and joy to our daily lives.

Parvati, is the personification of the desire, ambition, and bliss. She is the simple joy of the evolution of our days, weeks, months, and years, building towards and leaning into that which we become in life.

Shiva is able to transform because of Parvati's deep devotion. While Shiva performs the Tandava- a vigorous and intense dance, Parvati presents the Lasya, a graceful, sensual dance. While Shiva carries tools in his dance and things crumble around him, Parvati has nothing but herself, and life springs up around her. Shiva is creation through transformation.

Parvati is transformation through devotion. Devotions through which mountains are moved. Along with Shiva, Parvati symbolizes the harmonious union between the masculine and feminine forms of existence or the inextricable male and female beginning. In the Indian mythology, this union is called Shiva – Ardhanarishvara – this kind of iconography is symbolic and shows the inseparability of the female and male energies. This depiction of Mahadeva (Shiva) and his consort Parvati (in a combined and inseparable form) is one of the most well known and significant images of the two major Brahmanical deities and is also an expression of the indivisible fusion of both the male and female energies without which the Universe ceases to exist.

This harmony is particularly well expressed in both the dances – the Tandava and the Lasya performed by Shiva and Parvati. Apart from being a symbol of the cosmic creation and destruction, Tandava dance is also perceived as a symbol of the natural cycle of both life and death.

The medieval Sanskrit treatises of India have classified dance into three distinct categories, viz., natya, nritya, and nritya. These texts significantly characterize dancing as masculine or Tandava and feminine i.e., Lasya (Vatsyayan, 1968). In contrast to the Tandava dance, texts mention about the dance which is known as Lasya or sukumara nritya particularly described in the Natyashastra (Nagar, 2005). The term Lasya, in the context of Indian mythology, describes the dance performed by the goddess Parvati. The very name of this dance form signifies beauty, grace, happiness and compassion. The rhythmical steps of this dance are full of harmony, grace and tenderness and are supplementing to the rough male energy of the dance of Shiva. It is a symbol of the harmony of the ancient tempo of the creation of the world. The Abhinayadarpana clearly describes Lasya as derived from Parvati who taught it to Usha, the daughter of Vana (Ghosh, 2018).

In Indian art the images of Parvati have been found in her variegated and splendid forms. Majority of her images are associated with lord Shiva but single images are also numerous in stone and metal. Among many iconographical representations, her dancing form deserves special mention. Her gestures express the intellect, power of nature and the protection of the believers.

Figure 1 Dancing image of Parvati in metal

A unique dancing image of Parvati in metal has been recovered from the coastal area of West Bengal. The image has been found from Maipit, Sundarban and presently it is preserved in Dr. Tulsi Charan Bhattacharya Smriti Sangrahasala (museum). This image of Parvati stands on a pedestal in a dancing pose. Her bent left leg is upraised and right leg rests on the pedestal in a typical classical dance form. Adorned with many ornaments, like karnakuldala, hara, balaya and long conical kiritamukuta, the figure shows a unique Kapidhahasta pose of the classical dance style of Bharatanatyam. The goddess shows the Lasya dance reflecting the joyous mood and happiness.

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